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PROCEEDING **AISTEEL**

**THE FIRST ANNUAL INTERNATIONAL SEMINAR
ON TRANSFORMATIVE EDUCATION
AND EDUCATIONAL LEADERSHIP**

DEVELOPING FUTURE TEACHERS' EDUCATIONAL MODEL

**Medan, November 19th, 2016
Auditorium Building - UNIMED**

ORGANIZED BY :
POST GRADUATE SCHOOL, STATE UNIVERSITY OF MEDAN
NORTH SUMATERA - INDONESIA
JLN. WILLEM ISKANDAR PSR. V - MEDAN ESTATE

Proceedings of The First Annual International Seminar on Transformative Education and Educational Leadership (AISTEEL 2016)

“Developing Future Teachers’ Educational Model”

State University of Medan, North Sumatera, Indonesia
November, 19th 2016

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Chairman Foreword

The honorable,

- *Professor Peter Charles Taylor, PhD, Director of Transformative Education Research Centre and a Professor of STEAM Education at Murdoch University, Perth - Western Australia*
- *Associate Professor Elisabeth Taylor, PhD, an expert in Curriculum Theory, Peace Education, Science Education at Murdoch University, Perth - Western Australia*
- *Professor Dr. Nurahimah Mohd. Yusuf, Professor of Curriculum and Instruction at School of Education, University Utara Malaysia*
- *Prof. Dr. Mukhlas Samani, M.Pd., an expert in National Curriculum at Ministry of Education and Culture, Indonesia*
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- *Deans of Faculties of Education, Languages and Arts, Social Sciences, Natural Sciences and Mathematics, Engineering, Sports Sciences, and Economics*
- *Director of Postgraduate School of UNIMED*
- *Lecturers, researchers, students, all speakers and participants*

Assalamualaikum Wr Wb

Good Morning, *Salam Sejahtera*, Praise to Allah the Almighty for all His blessing, where today we are here to participate in ‘The First Annual International Seminar on Transformative Education and Educational Leadership’ with the theme “Developing Future Teachers’ Education Model”.

Ladies and Gentlemen,

This seminar presents a keynote speaker, 5 guest speakers from Australia, Malaysia and Indonesia and 132 researchers covering lecturers, teachers and students with around 860 participants. The researchers come from Manado, Palu, Kendari, Malang, Surabaya, Solo, Bandung, Jakarta, Palembang, Jambi, Batam, Pekanbaru, Padang, Aceh, Medan and North Sumatera.

I would like to express greatest thankful to all colleagues in the steering committee for cooperation in administering and arranging the seminar. Hopefully this seminar will be continued in the coming years with many more insight articles from inspiring research.

Wassalamualaikum Wr. Wb.

Rahmad Husein

Welcoming Speech of Director of Postgraduate Study State University of Medan

Best wishes for all of us,

First of all thanks to God who has given grace and health to us so that we can assemble this place to attend The First Annual International Seminar on Transformative Education and Educational Leadership (AISTEEL) 2016. This seminar is organized by Postgraduate Study (PPs) of the State University of Medan (Unimed). Welcome to all keynote speakers, researchers, students and, participants.

This international seminar is one of the manifestations of the vision and mission of PPs of Unimed, namely the dissemination and implementation of the results of research and studies related to the community. Therefore we strongly support the activities of this seminar which is also a series of academic activities of Unimed. Through this seminar, the participants will exchange information related to the latest research in the field of Transformative Education and Educational Leadership, which is expected to bring new ideas in solving various problems that arise particularly in the world of education.

In accordance with the theme presented in this seminar “Developing Future Teachers Education Model” it is expected that PPs Unimed can lead and strengthen the future teachers. The goal of transformative education is to develop visionary teachers and teacher educators to be capable of and committed to transforming education systems worldwide so that they prepare citizens with high-level abilities for solving global crises such as internationally political conflicts, climate change and loss of biocultural diversity.

Thank you for all committee to has well organized this seminar. Thanks to all keynote speakers who have attended, presented and shared their ideas on transformative education and educational leadership. Thanks to all researchers, students and participants and hopefully this will be scientific discussion to develop the future education.

Finally, I hope that all academicians and stakeholders of PPs Unimed hand-in-hand to excel our institution to be a world class university.

Best wishes for all of us

Director,

Prof. Dr. Bornok Sinaga, M.Pd

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GAME AS A MEDIUM FOR PRESERVATION NATION CULTURES

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Abstract - Advances in Information Technology and Communication (ICT) since the discovery of internet had made human beings can communicate with each other anywhere in the world without being constrained by the living room area and different times. Various global information is able to get quickly and easily from anywhere without any restriction of nationality and statehood. Online games are also the sprung mass. As a result of this could bring positive or negative influence on social order, cultures, ideology, and ethics in a society that is quite dangerous that can affect the values of nationalism to the nation. Opportunities and challenges have developed innovation by combining the technology game with elements of cultures. Games that contain elements of national cultures has expected used as a medium contribution in preserving the national cultures.

Keywords: ICT, game, culture, nationalism, society

1 INTRODUCTION

Culture determines the way in which individuals identify and recognize one another within their own social sphere of action and the traditional cultures and value systems on them constitute the factor for social harmony, and give a special cultural identity to the members of a community which, in itself, is one of the needs for endogenous development. Culture is a legacy of ancestors or our ancestors priceless. Culture is also a national identity compulsory respected and retained and preserved so that the culture is not lost and became a legacy of our children and grandchildren someday.

In the compulsory process of social evolution and change which emanates from the introduction of values and models of external behaviour inspired by the advent of foreign technologies the cultural system in their entirety are attacked upon.

Indonesia is an archipelago, stretching from Sabang to Merauke, which is arranged in thousands of large and small islands, connected by various straits and sea. Today the island listed and totaled 13,466 islands.[5] As an archipelago country has a diversity of customs and culture that spread evenly across the country. According to BPS data last in year 2010 there are 1,340 ethnic groups in Indonesia.[6]

West Sumatra is an area that has a variety of traditional folk art. Art that is still there that have not recognized it. One of the problems in the Minangkabau of West Sumatra is difficult to get information about the arts are still many, this is due to lack of attention from local governments in providing information about the arts Minang to the next generation, and other factors of there is not of communication provided to give information about the arts of Minangkabau of West Sumatra.

Advances in Information Technology and Communication (ICT) and transport into to make be faster of globalization. Globalization is sweeping across the globe have an impact for the social culture of a nation. At first, globalization is felt only in major cities in Indonesia. Globalization is spreading very widely and quickly brought positive and negative impacts. Currently, Indonesian children more easily influenced by western values into Indonesia through the Internet, television, and print media and much imitated by the public. A result of these conditions will impact many Indonesian children who will be more familiar with foreign cultures than the native culture of his people.

Thus, the need to raise awareness of important culture in which the culture of Indonesia is the local culture is the duty of every society, where the role of each of those who continue to strive to inherit the power of local culture will be a cultural force it to stay there.

Technology is a means in the service of a superior objective that is the better recognition of nature and a more suitable utilization of nature, and safeguarding the cultural identity as a factor for the solidarity and a requisite for the survival of nation, we have to know that the best technology is not the most modern technology.

Development in technology, particularly information and communication technology in the past decade has brought a very big change in the areas of life including education activities. ICT get developed with a game that can give information to the public about a culture in this research have exempted from the Minang culture.

Macromedia Flash applications used to create the game. This game consists of two games, namely Guess Pictures, and Puzzles (Arrange Figures). All games provide information and learning about the arts in Minang, such as Dance, Musical Instruments, traditional clothes of Minang, Minang Art Exhibition as well as some songs are from Minang.

Development of educational game applications in the arts of Minang community as users who are not familiar with any description of these, so to see and play educational game's application will recognize the arts of Minang. This game provides information as well as a medium of learning for anyone when and wherever they are. Thus, with innovations such as this, it has expected the knowledge of Indonesian cultures, especially in West Sumatra (Minang) will increase and the expected application users will be more love the arts in their home country.

2. EDUCATIONAL GAME

Much has been said about the impact of technology on the educational systems of the Third World and also on the aesthetic values. We emphasized mainly on negative cultural aspects of technology. But we live in a world which is reliant on technology where the motivating power of national development constitutes that technology. Although it is recognized that technical devices have been designed in response to the determined cultural needs and their compatibility with the goals of another culture requires great endeavour.

An educational game is a game designed to teach humans about a specific subject and to teach them a skill. As educators, governments, and parents realize the psychological need and benefits of gaming have on learning, this educational tool has become mainstream. Games are interactive play that teaches us goals, rules, adaptation, problem solving, interaction, all represented as a story.

They give us the fundamental needs of learning by providing - enjoyment, passionate involvement, structure, motivation, ego gratification, adrenaline, creativity, social interaction and emotion. "Play has a deep biological, evolutionarily important, function, which has to do specifically with learning." [4]

There are logic games, simulation games, computer educational games, board games, and brain games. There is no right or wrong in games. However, my choice of games is to play board games - games that you play around the table with your family or friends. These types of games have the added benefit of providing great family time at the same time as building educational skills. Additionally, when you play a game at a table with others you have opportunity to have all kinds of examples before your turn which will help you when your turn comes around. You have an opportunity to learn strategy from each other too. Having examples or 'modeling' helps to improve learning skills too.

Learning games are not just a genre of games, but a unique and emerging that operates at the intersection of game designers, learning designers, subject matter experts, developers, educators and researchers, who collaborate to produce innovative and powerfully engaging learning experiences.

Teachers, parents, and learners all need and often request of game designers a better understanding of what a game is targeting, how that situates into a larger learning sequence, and how they know what they've learned from the game.

The Four-dimensional framework has been proposed by de Freitas & Jarvis (2006), as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Four – Dimensional Framework (de Freitas & Jarvis, 2006)

The work done and portrayed within the framework shows that this model comprises of four basic principles, as follows: [1]

- 1) Context. Each game is characterized by a specific context that will guide the scenarios as well as the ways students and teachers will interact with its features. During the context's establishment, one must define characteristics such as required infrastructure, technical specifications, location of usage, type of game (e.g. role playing, multiplayer etc), activities to be performed etc.
- 2) Representation. This concept refers to all representations that are required to be properly portrayed within the game. For example, each player needs to be represented by avatars that will have specific characteristics based on the context of the game. Additionally, the virtual world should represent interesting scenery that will be integrated with all the features of the game in a harmonized and meaningful way. Successful representation is vital for the increased motivation of students, since they need to be intrigued in order to want to learn by playing. An important metric that can determine this is the quality of the graphics employed during the representation, which needs to be high so that it can create better and more immersive simulations.
- 3) Learner. This concept relates to all features corresponding to the learner within the game. Some of these include the ages of the students to be taught, their preferences, the availability and level of previous knowledge on the specific learning domain, our learning objectives regarding the game's learning outcomes etc. Additionally, it is considered important by the relevant literature to try and promote learning through groups in educational games (Sandford, 2006), as collaborative learning is gradually being employed in education.
- 4) Pedagogy. The most important factor that distinguishes an educational game from a computer game is the pedagogical aspect, i.e. the fact that the entire game and its activities are developed in order to fulfil learning objectives and to result in learning outcomes. To this end, the development of such games should depend on the study and incorporation of learning strategies. These strategies later on determine how the game will be integrated into the learning process so that it will produce the desired outcomes. Some representative examples of employed learning strategies are problem-based learning or experiential based learning, which allow a variety of pedagogical models for learning processes, especially when they use online technologies.[1] The pedagogies used should promote learning processes that will be

constructivist and cognitive so that they will allow the creation of new knowledge by the students as well as their in depth comprehension of the taught material through active and collaborative participation. Additionally, learning processes have to be instructive and associative, that is they are required to progress in a logical manner and provide assistance when needed. Finally, collaborative learning when knowledge is exchanged through practice is also a feature that should be supported by learning processes within educational games.[2]

3. GAME DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

People interested in educational uses of games will find much of value to them. Discussion of pedagogical principles that underlie games, techniques for game development, factors to consider when using games, or a rich variety of examples demonstrating how games could be used in various subject matters and at different educational levels.

In develop of an application is the design phase of the construction process is very important to decide how the system will be developing. This game designed by the Four-Dimensional Framework has proposed by De Freitas & Jarvis.[1] It intended that application Game be easily used by the user (user-friendly). Each game supports a different set of the features included in the list as well as of the features shown.

Image stacking game (puzzle) have designed only in three layers. The first and the second layer is a layer that holds scripts for game development. While the third layer, is a layer that has ten frames. In this third layer frames used are five frames.

Each frame designed two pictures placed on the two areas that accommodated by a single tool that is the Rectangle Tool. In the first to fourth frames described how the original image is nine pieces of the picture that will appear when the game played and clicked the button scrambled. To make dots pattern on the original image disordered with images that to do prepared in giving the name of the column Convert To Symbol. The name has created as a Movie Clip (Type) for each piece of the picture. Each piece of the image converted to a movie clip symbol and named. Then the second piece of the picture until the ninth. Overall the image slices named Bag1-bag9. Bag1-bag9 is the name of the symbol in the original image that cut for randomization images. The patterns on a blank area of the image that is the place to pieces of the image that compiled into an overall picture as the original image, as shown in Figure 2.

The pieces of images in the picture area are empty, named by bagAs1 - bagAs9 then coupled with the name of the Instance Name. In addition, it is also given a one-timer to regulate the speed of preparation of the image into the original image completely. If time runs out, the game stops and the frame immediately leads to a frame 10 which indicates that the game finished (Game Over).

Hardware used to run this game only a Personal Computer (PC) with a Windows operating system that has equipped with a flash player application. If this PC have not installed a flash player, it will be free of charge to download at the website: <https://get.adobe.com/flashplayer/>

Figure 2: Game Puzzle Design

When players click the choice puzzle game, it will show the original image before the images at random and one area where the image will realign the original scene. In addition, there are also three buttons namely the random, repeat button, and a back button. Pieces of the picture will randomize into pieces the images rearranged in the blank area. Repeat button used to look back at the original images that previously have disordered. On the Application of this game will be able to get some information about the traditional clothes, dances, traditional houses and traditional weapons on the Minangkabau people, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Information Provided Game

4. CONCLUSIONS

The Evolutionists introduced technology as the major element of culture and put the other components at second place holding that all the components of culture have affected by technology. The configuration of computer games so as they can be integrated the educational domain has generated a new trend in technologies used for education called educational games. Information Technology and Communication makes it easy to create a variety of game applications. Educational-game should not merely a transfer of educational content in digital form, but used also as an information medium to convey a moral message and cultures of a nation.

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